

Rejuvenation[©]

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Abstract

Cell Sonic has been saving lives for many years by curing chronic diseases, something that biochemists cannot do. It is now evident that Cell Sonic's improvement in lives goes further, it makes people biologically younger. This article examines two cases in detail. The ladies are both 59 years old and live on opposite sides of the world.

Keywords: Chronic disease, cancer, telomeres, stress, criticism, rejuvenate, lupus, Susan, Wendy.

Introduction

About three years ago, I wrote the article entitled "From Paradise to Hell and Back[©], How Cancer was Cured in Ten Seconds" about Susan. I called her Susan to keep her identity private but now she wants to tell you her real name because she feels that the benefits she got have to be shared with everyone.

In the picture below, she is the girl in the middle with CellSonic customers who had flown in their own plane to collect a CellSonic machine for their clinic.

The lady is Wendy Zolezzi in California. She went on to buy a Cell Sonic machine, opened her own clinic, and became a distributor for CellSonic. This made her younger.

We get a closer view of Wendy in a photo received in November 2023.

Wendy is in the center in a red dress. The lady on the left is also a CellSonic clinic owner and the man is a CellSonic engineer. The changes affecting Wendy were apparent to all and for her 59th birthday, they got her a cake marking the age they believed.

Wendy was delighted but needed to know more. She spent \$500 with [TruDiagnostic.com](https://www.trudiagnostic.com) and with their kit sent them a sample of her blood. They analyzed it and produced a forty-page report. Here are some of the results.

It says she is 8.18 years younger than her calendar age. The methods that Tru Diagnostic uses are shown in detail in a video on their website.

They also reported reductions in these cases by the stated percentages

Death risk	-79.03%
Disease risk	-72.50%
Cancer risk	-50.46%
Heart disease	-57.00%
Stroke	-54.09%
Type 2 diabetes	-51.01%
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	-37.42%
Depression	-36.48%

The significance is apparent when remembering that three years earlier Wendy was dying from throat cancer, had broken bones, and severe back pain.

Copied from the report

We use epigenetic biomarker proxies to predict genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics sum values that are positive for your aging, and some that are negative for your aging. In the graph below you will see the factors contributing to your aging the most. If a bar is above zero, it increases your OMICm Age, if, below zero, it decreases your OMICm Age.

Your Clinical Epigenetic Biomarker Proxies (EBP)

Your Metabolites Epigenetic Biomarker Proxies (EBP)

Your Protein Epigenetic Biomarker Proxies (EBP)

Telomere Length

If we were to estimate your biological age strictly from your telomere measurement, we would anticipate your age to be:

51.26
YEARS OLD

Telomere Length Based on Biological Age Prediction:

Your Average telomere prediction length:
7.1 kb
This puts you in the:
74.59th Percentile

According to the analysis of the blood sample, Wendy's biological age is 51.26 years having been born 59 years ago. She was dying three years ago; this is a remarkable recovery that is more than a smile and smooth complexion. Here is an explanation of telomere taken from [Telomere \(genome.gov\)](https://www.genome.gov)

Telomere. A chromosome is essentially a long, long piece of DNA that has wrapped up and compacted on itself until it looks like the structure you probably picture when I say chromosome. The problem is that the long piece of DNA has two ends, and they're just hanging out there loose. A lot of things

could go wrong if those ends aren't protected. They could get cut off, or they could join onto other loose DNA ends, which would be a problem for the cell. Telomeres are how cells protect chromosome ends. The telomere itself is a long stretch of a specific short DNA sequence repeated over and over hundreds of times. At the very end of the telomere is a sort of knot called the "T-loop," which keeps the chromosome ends from all sticking together. Every time a cell divides, some of those telomere repeats get cut off. So, in certain cell types that divide a lot, an enzyme called "telomerase" adds those repeats back, so the telomere doesn't get too short.

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Helga

Before delving into the changes made to Wendy by CellSonic we should look at another lady of the same age who is also getting younger after CellSonic treatments. This is Helga who knows little English but thankfully the CellSonic operator, Jette, is fluent in English and has supplied detailed medical information. Before buying a CellSonic machine, Jette twice took a group of patients to Poland for treatment. Helga was in both groups and Jette was very worried at first that Helga would not survive the journey. She could not climb steps and walking up the stairs at the hotel took ages with stops after each step. Her lungs were close to collapse, there was a huge wound on

her leg and her body was wracked with pain. After the first CellSonic treatment, Helga's strength increased, and she managed the hotel stairs without stopping. The other members of the group remarked on this, and it gave them all encouragement.

Helga was first diagnosed with arthritis, but it was more than that and in 2003 a hospital said the problem was SLE which is systemic lupus erythematosus, an autoimmune disease for which the establishment's biochemistry-based hospitals have no remedy. Helga's Body Mass Index was 14 and is now 17,

still too low but rising. Her lungs, kidneys, and skin had failed. Anorexia had led to a hernia in the stomach from violent retching trying to vomit. Helga

could not speak as she had inhalers in constant use and could not breathe without them.

Here is a translated background we compiled from Helga

Helga's parents were young, around 18-20 years old, when they had Helga. She was not a planned child. Later came a sister and brother, and the boy became schizophrenic.

The father was very harsh and slapped the children if they came home late or disobeyed.

Helga was the eldest and not so bright at school, she had inferiority complexes compared to her younger sister who was very capable, domineering, and bossy to Helga. There was a competition between the girls. Helga remembers it as her sister and mother standing together against her. When Helga is about 14 years old, she is teased by her mother and sister for

saying she is fat and develops eating disorders, anorexia, and bulimia and loses 15 kg.

Helga married a man she met when she was 16. He is domineering and constantly criticizing, but they are still together.

Helga falls ill and develops the disease lupus and rheumatoid arthritis. She consults a psychologist and understands the context of saying no to her dominant sister and husband. She's getting a little better at speaking up.

The relationship with the sister is still very poor and the sister continues attacking Helga verbally. Helga's mother was an alcoholic and died last year of liver cirrhosis. Her father had died when Helga was aged 42.

Helga in 2022 and early 2024.

When Jette got her own machine with many patients needing treatment, Helga was already a regular visitor to the clinic. As well as getting treatments herself, she became a support nurse and was given a Cellsonic tunic and badge. Helga speaks too fast to be understood. This is ostracising her. It is a result of being afraid to speak to her mother and sister. Jette wants her to get speech therapy.

The time lag between the illnesses of Susan and Helga and the causes is about twenty years. A person does not just catch cancer or just get arthritis. They are caused by a breakdown in the immune system caused by a failure of the mind to maintain a positive outlook on life. Wendy and Helga are not unique. What happened to them is happening now to millions of others, male and female, and the statisticians will report that cancer is increasing despite less smoking.

A factor that the medical establishment is denying is the fact that spiked proteins in the COVID-19 viruses, especially Pfizer and Moderna, are causing younger, previously fit people, to develop cancer which immediately shows as stage 4. All doctors are seeing this in all countries and their managers are refuting the information. It did not affect Wendy and Helga because it posted their plights. However, both Wendy and Jette, being active now in the medical field, are now witnessing this phenomenon.

Wendy married a singer after a disturbing childhood and teenage and became his trophy wife on the glamorous Hollywood set. Her brain power was not wanted, and she was not allowed to express ideas. This led to throat cancer and all her other problems. Her mind was distorted. See the brain as hardware in computer terms. The mind is the software and Wendy was running the wrong program.

Helga was similarly bullied and attacked until she became ill. It wasn't cancer, but it was equally devastating. Her ability to speak was impaired because of fear of speaking and being rebuked.

CellSonic clinics are now seeing that the cause of chronic disease goes back many years. The CellSonic treatment corrects the disease. Cancer is changed in a few minutes from malignant to benign. The cell voltages are lifted. Cell voltages elsewhere are also lifted and revert to normal behavior. It is not the appearance of a cell as seen through an electron microscope that shows its condition, it is the behavior of the cell; a static picture does not reveal the

problem. Pharmaceuticals are useless for chronic diseases. The problem is electrical and that is what CellSonic corrects safely and quickly. That is half the job.

The other half is to correct the software program; get their minds on the right track, enjoy the beauty in the world around them, replace criticism with praise, letting them feel loved. Again, no drugs can do this, and certainly no surgery. There is nothing wrong with their brain, so never try anti-depressants, or brain-damaging drugs that should be illegal. The damaging thoughts have to be pushed aside by pleasant thoughts. Conversation is needed, and the patient craves it. If CellSonic therapists have a problem, it is that the patient wants to be adopted, married, or cuddled and stay forever at the clinic where they have found what they lost so many years ago. Amazingly, CellSonic operators are good at this, and then we have to coach the therapists on how to leave their clients' problems at the clinic lest they too become affected by gloom.

The Law

Legally in most countries, a physical attack is illegal. Verbal abuse is bad and allowed in the name of free speech. Lawmakers should understand that there is a difference between political debate and incessant abuse that permanently damages a person. If it had not been for CellSonic, Wendy and Helga would have been killed by the words used against them 20 or 30 years before. Their attackers, family members, were not only damaging these two girls but also creating harm in their social circle. In other words, it is legal to kill someone by nagging, mocking, and criticizing them for everything they do. The mocking critics are always failures driven by jealousy trying to drag others down to their level. They have many victims and the most suffering they cause is to themselves. Such people are to be avoided.

The answer

It is impossible for law enforcers to hear what is said behind closed doors, hidden microphones apart, and monitored by AI-programmed listening

devices, so legal protection is not practical. Nevertheless, monitoring is possible, and the Sapiens Shield plan I have devised works to find a problem before it develops and stops it.

After a twenty-minute diagnosis and cure in a Sapiens Shield clinic with CellSonic, the person goes to the next room to meet Granny, an intuitive old lady who senses that the person is from a dysfunctional family and can see on their card that they have cancer, for example, up to a few minutes ago, now converted to benign. Granny will listen. She is not in a white coat and is not judgmental. The person will talk with confidence. The result is an invitation to help this person escape from their torment at home.

This process which applied in primitive societies has been lost in the modern era, where mass communication devices separate everyone and enable mass attacks by anonymous people who are themselves total failures. The plight of Wendy and Helga is to be seen everywhere and can be avoided by the Sapiens Shield. The medical establishment and the politicians they manipulate have to wake up to the dangers they are allowing lest they have no population left worth dominating. The standard of living of the elite depends on everyone having a high standard of living. Exploiting the masses is the way for the elite to collapse.

How to Rejuvenate

From the examples of Wendy and Helga, we understand the process. CellSonic treatments lift the body cell voltages to the correct level of 75 MV. Reassurances by the therapists help the patients to maintain cell voltages. They are not tormented by memories, are eating wisely, exercising more, and sleeping better. They are making friends instead of enemies. This has restored their health.

The next stage of reducing biological age is simple, fascinating, and a lesson in how to live. Both ladies saw the benefits of their CellSonic treatments and wanted to offer them to others so that they too would be helped. Wendy bought a CellSonic, opened a clinic, and became a distributor for the company. Helga, too, was also involved in Jette's group of supporters and performed the CellSonic treatments on patients. Compared to Wendy, Helga was weaker, but compared to how she had been before she had her first treatment in Poland, she became stronger. Climbing up from the depths takes time and Helga understands this.

Both ladies are in the presence of the electrical field when handling the CellSonic machine. This proves the safety of the system and suggests a benefit from the uplifting of a hundred or so pulses each of one billionth of a second duration. Not much, but sufficient to rejuvenate the electrical creature that we are. So, if you want longer telomeres, have CellSonic treatments and give the same treatments to others.

Postscript

Hi Andrew,

You are so wise! Great paper!! I feel honored that you wanted to include me in it.

I believe that CellSonic was a big part of my reversing my cancer, PTSD, anxiety, brain fog, and more. I also believe the changes I made in diet, detoxing, exercise, and supplementation all played a part in the overall

healing as my body was able to hold the charge CS delivered. I worked hard for six months before ever getting treated. I think people should know this. CellSonic raised my voltage and, because my cells were cleaned out of toxins, my thoughts alighted in a healthy way (released negative programs), along with supporting my body with proper vitamins, and minerals all played a part in activating dormant stem cells. It was truly a package for me.

In learning Biological Decoding, it has been scientifically proven that chronic illness comes after a traumatic event, whether real or imagined. The body goes into a "repair" phase, which is why the body creates the cells that need attention. So, the torture put upon poor "Helga" by years of being in a family that delivered abusive behavior towards her is sickening but super clear to me why she ended up self-torturing and with a chronic disease. I would like to investigate more about the timeline of Helga and when her current issues arise.

Although I experienced trauma in my childhood from my alcoholic, emotionally unavailable father, my trauma was because of my 15-year relationship and marriage to a colossal narcissist. Verbal, psychological, and emotional abuse through gaslighting and devaluation is the true reason I got stage three metastatic thyroid cancer that spread to my neck and lungs after I left him.

Are you planning to leave the statements saying "Cured"?

Again. I love this paper. So, valuable, and, I believe someone reading this will relate and understand that their illness comes from a broken-down immune system allowing the lack of cellular voltage that prevents the body from healing. As you taught me. broken down cells require raising the voltage after cleaning out the cells, negative thoughts, and toxins including toxic people. Reverse the programs the software is running. CellSonic is a huge piece of this along with doing the work on items I mentioned above. It's pieces of the pie.

I proclaim myself to be your #1 fan! You changed my life, and I am forever grateful. Is it possible for you to expand on the fact that CS activates Stem cells?? I love that as it directly relates to the telomeres being lengthened.

Postscript

Wendy attaches a lot of importance to her diet and health supplements and, for sure, they are important. In so doing, she is being positive. She is determined to recover her health. This is her mind running the correct software and whether it is supplements or thoughts that are most important is not a useful argument; they both played a part in her recovery.

What she has ignored is how she chose to marry the wrong man. As we now know, she is intelligent and would have been when she got married, but she made an almost fatal mistake. Many people make these mistakes. Why and how? Because they were unable to evaluate their chosen one. The education system that supposedly prepares us for adulthood does not help. From conversations with Wendy, I learned that her teenage years were turbulent. The expected glamour of a famous singer appealed. How was she to know what was behind the scenes?

The cause of chronic disease can be said to be relationships. Forming the appropriate relationships is necessary to avoid chronic disease. Thus, as curing chronic disease involves finding and correcting the cause, it involves

helping people to make good relationships. That is a huge subject ranging from arranged marriages to the role of religion, the laws about divorce and so

on that are beyond this article. Then who should educate everyone so that the next generation does not grow up in a toxic family?

Writing articles is more than a sit-down and type operation. A lot of thought goes into the planning of what to include and what to leave out so that the reader can follow the trail. Saving a person's life and then making them biologically younger, is a complex story that has to be simplified to be understood. It also has to be approved by the subjects, in this case, Wendy and Helga. Just as I had received Wendy's approval and signed it off with my personal touch (I have been cycling for 72 years), in comes a message from Jette.

Went to Helga's 60 birthday.

Her husband said "Helga, I love you very much" at least 10 times He is so grateful. Maybe he realizes, she speaks up now. Add to the article and I can use it here.

I just read it, very, very good.

And the perfect man, thanks for the advice.

Her husband celebrating Anne with a limousine, driving with the family here her two daughters-in-law.

Conclusion

That's what we want to see after millions of dollars invested in developing CellSonic and great efforts to demonstrate that biophysics works. Rejuvenating and making people happy is our reward. We love you all.

Andrew

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